

N3C Query Report: Medications and Treatments Currently in Use for PASC Patients

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Introduction to the analysis

The N3C team was asked to evaluate the use of medications and treatments in patients identified by our classification as potentially having long-COVID/PASC. Below we first describe the cohort definition used for the analysis and why this specific cohort was identified. We then provide an overview of medications and treatments used commonly in this cohort at the time of PASC diagnosis. We conclude with an overview of caveats and considerations for our next set of inquiries regarding therapeutics, with the hope that these next steps will support candidate evaluation for further investigation in prospective studies.

Denominator

The denominator is defined as any patient in N3C with a U09.9 ICD-10-CM diagnosis code (Post COVID-19 condition, unspecified) ($n = 7,730$). This approach was chosen to identify patients with PASC, as the diagnosis code enables us to set a “PASC index date” that we can use in all subsequent analyses. Twenty-five of the 70 N3C contributing sites are currently using this diagnosis code, which became available for use in EHRs as of October 1, 2021.

A demographic breakdown of these patients follows in **Table 1**. In accordance with the N3C download policy, for demographics where small cell sizes (<20 patients) could be derived from context, we have shifted the counts by a random number between -5 and 5. The accompanying percentages reflect the shifted number.

For future analyses, we plan to also incorporate PASC patients who do not have a clear index date into the cohort. As the U09.9 diagnosis code only became available on October 1, 2021, identifying PASC patients prior to this date is critical but will require an alternate approach, which we propose [in this work](#) and continue to refine.

Table 1. Patients in N3C with a U09.9 diagnosis code. Patients have been stratified by whether they were hospitalized at the time of their U09.9 diagnosis code.

	Hospitalized @ U09.9 <i>n</i> = 1,317	Not Hospitalized @ U09.9 <i>n</i> = 6,413
Sex (%)		
female	623 (47.3)	4,128 (64.4)
male	692 (52.5)	2,281 (35.6)
unknown	<20	<20
Race (%)		
Asian	20 (1.5)	103 (1.6)
Black	225 (17.1)	764 (11.9)
Hawaiian/Pac. Isld.	<20	<20
White	937 (71.1)	4,809 (75.0)
Other	<20	54 (0.8)
Unknown	111 (8.4)	660 (10.3)
Ethnicity (%)		
Hispanic/Latino	139 (10.6)	599 (9.3)
Not Hispanic/Latino	1,126 (85.5)	5,481 (85.5)
Unknown	52 (3.9)	333 (5.2)
Age (%)		
0-4	<20	<20
5-9	41 (3.1)	29 (0.5)
10-15	30 (2.3)	93 (1.5)
16-20	<20	156 (2.4)
21-35	111 (8.4)	813 (12.7)
36-45	155 (11.8)	1132 (17.7)
46-55	183 (13.9)	1,311 (20.4)
56-65	246 (18.7)	1,236 (19.3)
66+	405 (30.8)	1,074 (16.7)

Objective 1: Characterize medications prescribed to patients diagnosed with PASC

Figure 1. Exposure to Systemic Antivirals and Corticosteroids around PASC Diagnosis. This figure shows the percent of patients in the cohort (y-axis) exposed to systemic antiviral medications (e.g. remdesivir, left panel) or systemic corticosteroids (a common class of antiinflammatory medications e.g., dexamethasone, right panel) over time (x-axis). The y-axis in this figure is not cumulative. The figure is centered on the U09.9 index date, defined as the first calendar day when each patient had that code in their record. Results are stratified by whether patients were hospitalized (red) or not (blue) at the time of their U09.9 diagnosis.

Overall, few outpatients diagnosed with PASC were prescribed systemic antivirals either at the time of their diagnosis or thereafter. Inpatient antiviral use is higher (5-6% at time of PASC diagnosis), but may reflect uncertainty on the part of clinicians and patients about whether symptoms represent re-infection or PASC. However, steroid use is much higher and may represent a hypothesis to be tested prospectively; steroids are given to 7-8% of outpatients and ~30% of inpatients at the time of their diagnosis with PASC. It is reasonable to hypothesize that the prominence of pulmonary features and diagnostic testing (see below) likely drives some of this steroid use.

ATC Main Level Medications

cumulative percent of U09.9 patients with exposure
1317 Hospitalized patients; 6413 Not Hospitalized patients

Figure 2. Exposure to Classes of Medications After PASC Diagnosis. This figure shows the cumulative proportion of patients in the cohort (y-axis), stratified by whether or not they were hospitalized at the time of their PASC diagnosis, who received each of the medication classes shown (each facet shows one medication class) over time (x-axis) after the PASC index date.

Although these results are at a high level (see **Figure 1** for greater granularity), they do indicate that patients diagnosed with PASC are most often exposed to medications targeting the gastrointestinal/metabolic, hematologic, cardiovascular, and nervous systems in addition to anti-infectives in the 12 weeks following PASC diagnosis.

Objective 2: Characterize diagnostics and treatments performed on or shortly after PASC index

Figure 3. Percent of PASC patients with procedures after diagnosis. This figure shows the cumulative proportion of patients in the cohort (y-axis) who were not hospitalized at the time of their PASC diagnosis who received each of the procedures shown (each facet shows one procedure) over time (x-axis) after the PASC index date. Patients who were hospitalized at the time of their U09.9 diagnosis were excluded because they were exposed to many procedures that were more likely related to inpatient care than PASC. Procedures were selected because they are common after PASC diagnosis (see Table 3 below).

Intriguing and potentially hypothesis-generating results for trials in this figure include that some patients are receiving physical (~7% within 90 days) and occupational therapy (~2% within 90 days), that ~14% receive injections (possibly for pain) within 90 days, and that ~4% receive vaccinations, presumably some of which are for SARS-CoV-2 and may be in an attempt to reduce PASC symptoms based on anecdotal reports of benefit.

Table 2. Diagnostic procedures for 6,413 non-hospitalized patients with PASC from 0 through 90 days after U09.9 diagnosis date. Counts reflect the number of patients exposed to each procedure at least once in the time period. Only procedures used for ≥ 29 of non-hospitalized patients are shown.

Procedure	Count of non-hospitalized patients exposed (%)	
Radiography/fluoroscopy	1400 (21.8)	
ECG	1007 (15.7)	
CT	738 (11.5)	
Spirometry	667 (10.4)	
Carbon monoxide diffusing capacity	579 (9.0)	
Echo	459 (7.2)	
Plethysmography	377 (5.9)	
Ultrasound	315 (4.9)	
MRI	260 (4.1)	
Pulmonary Stress Test	181 (2.8)	
Mammography / Breast tomography	174 (2.7)	
Venous Duplex Scan	166 (2.6)	
Gas dilution	155 (2.4)	
Pulse oximetry	148 (2.3)	
Surg path	139 (2.2)	
Psychotherapy / psychological testing	134 (2.1)	
Speech evaluation	130 (2.0)	
Ophthalmological diagnostics/services	117 (1.8)	
Cognitive / neurobehavior assessment	88 (1.4)	
Sleep study	74 (1.2)	
Respiratory flow volume loop	66 (1.0)	
Colonoscopy	65 (<1.0)	
Health Behavior Intervention / Assessment	60 (<1.0)	
Esophagogastroduodenoscopy	59 (<1.0)	
Blood typing, serologic; ABO	57 (<1.0)	
Ab screen, RBC, each serum technique	54 (<1.0)	
Blood typing, serologic; Rh (D)	53 (<1.0)	
COVID / RSV / flu test	53 (<1.0)	
Laryngoscopy	53 (<1.0)	
Swallowing function test / intervention	46 (<1.0)	
Needle electromyography	45 (<1.0)	
Functional residual capacity	44 (<1.0)	
Nerve conduction study	43 (<1.0)	
Endoscopy	43 (<1.0)	
Bone density study	33 (<1.0)	
Tympanometry	29 (<1.0)	

Perhaps not surprisingly, many of the most common diagnostic procedures after PASC diagnosis are for the cardiac (e.g., electrocardiography/EKG, echocardiography) and pulmonary (e.g., spirometry, CO diffusion capacity, plethysmography, pulmonary stress test) systems. Standard ionizing radiography (CT, radiography/fluoroscopy) is common but information is not immediately available about which body systems are being imaged. Meaningful minorities of patients received less common studies potentially associated with reported PASC symptoms including cognitive/neurobehavior assessments, ophthalmological diagnostics, and electromyography/nerve conduction studies.

Table 3. Treatment procedures for 6,413 non-hospitalized patients with PASC from 0 through 90 days after U09.9 diagnosis date. Counts reflect the number of patients exposed to each treatment at least once in the time period. Only procedures used for ≥ 29 non-hospitalized patients are shown.

Procedure	Count of non-hospitalized patients exposed (%)
Injection	840 (13.1)
PT	419 (6.5)
Vaccination	234 (3.6)
Infusion	170 (2.7)
Psychotherapy / psychological testing	134 (2.1)
Ophthalmological diagnostics / services	117 (1.8)
Self-care/home management training	117 (1.8)
OT	112 (1.7)
Manual therapy techniques*	99 (1.5)
Inhalation treatment	77 (1.2)
Psychiatric care	63 (<1.0)
Health Behavior Intervention / Assessment	60 (<1.0)
Swallowing function test/intervention	46 (<1.0)
Destruction of lesion	40 (<1.0)
Inhaler / nebulizer**	36 (<1.0)
Transitional Care Management Services	32 (<1.0)
Chemodenervation of muscles	29 (<1.0)

*e.g., mobilization/ manipulation, manual lymphatic drainage, manual traction

**Demonstration and/or evaluation of patient utilization of an aerosol generator, nebulizer, metered dose inhaler or IPPB device

These most common therapeutic procedures after PASC diagnosis reveal several potential interventions to be tested prospectively. Injections are among the most commonly received therapies. Presumably many of these are for pain, a commonly reported PASC symptom. Vaccination is also quite common, and some vaccinations seem likely to be for SARS-CoV-2 and in an attempt to reduce symptoms based on anecdotal reports of benefit. Physical manifestations of PASC appear to often be treated with physical and occupational therapy and self-care / home management training as well as manual therapy techniques and chemodenervation of muscles (e.g., botulinum toxin). Other activities of daily living are targeted with swallowing function assessments and therapy and transitional care services.

Next steps to gather real world evidence

Because many patients do not get a U09.9 diagnosis code until much later in their long-COVID course, we will derive a start/index date for such patients (such as those identified by our machine learning model). We note that analysis using the U09.9 code is limited because the code only became available for use in October 2021.

We also plan to run these same analyses examining our full long-COVID cohort that has been identified by our ML long-Covid classifier as per the prior manuscript, including improvements to that classifier.

We plan to perform further classification and clustering of the medications and procedures and examine temporal correlations both with viral variants as well as each patient's temporal progression (including timing of COVID-19 diagnoses and vaccination, hospitalization, etc.). Finally, to assess comparative effectiveness, we will also examine medications that are used less frequently but have positive outcome correlations.